

Condemnations at the University of Paris: Techniques Used for Restoring the Misplaced Borderline Between Orthodox and Heresy in the Thirteenth Century⁶³¹

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Abstract

*The main focus of this paper is the thirteenth-century condemnations at the University of Paris. These events reflected the conflict between scientific and theological doctrines in the High Middle Ages. The most imposing of all, the condemnation of 1277, is even regarded as "the birth of modern science" by renowned physicist and historian of science Pierre Duhem. The condemnations were the result of spreading newly translated literature including the philosophical and scientific works of Aristotle as well as commentaries and summaries of them by Arabic philosophers. While the philosophical side of the condemnation of 1277 has been deeply explored by numerous scholars, political and procedural aspects are frequently left aside. The paper tries to review the historical background of the cases of 1277 and previous condemnations that occurred at the University of Paris. It distinguishes similarities and differences between them, and underlines scholarly gaps that future research can inquire. For the methodology, I exploited the primary literature established in *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, where the lists of condemnations, university statutes, and Papal and episcopal letters are collected together as well as secondary literature, that conduced me to review the historical and theological background leading to the thirteenth-century condemnations and to present assumptions and resolutions concerning the condemnation of 1277 in existing scholarship.*

Keywords: Thirteenth-Century Condemnations – University of Paris – Condemnations of 1277

⁶³¹ This article was written nine months before I finished my MA thesis, *The Role of Ecclesiastical and Academic Authorities in the Thirteenth-Century Academic Condemnations* (CEU Vienna, 2024). The thesis is a continuation of the research started in this article and clarifies the ambiguities presented at the end of this work. It also has to be noted, that I used some parts of this article in my thesis.

Introduction

The thirteenth-century condemnations are a significant element of the history of the University of Paris. They not only reflected the views and debates of scholars and students of the period but also broadened and developed the field of philosophical and scientific thinking. In the thirteenth century, the border between theological and philosophical-scientific concepts in scholarly debates became unclear, which provoked ecclesiastical authorities to act against them. The initial part of this essay will discuss what caused the border to become perceived as misplaced. In the second place, six cases of thirteenth-century condemnations will be analysed. Finally, it will provide the historical background of the condemnation of 1277, the debates around the event, and the scholarly gaps that must be examined and clarified.

The Origins of Heretical Ideas

Several historians contend that there was no medieval philosophy in the Christian West until the integration of Aristotelian and Arabic literature in the thirteenth century.⁶³² However, this does not seem true when one observes the thoughts, reasoning, and main interests of tenth, eleventh, and twelfth-century scholars. There were indeed no philosophers or texts dedicated to philosophy as such; however, philosophical discussions and speculations were apparently present. One manifestation of this is the hostile, or rather suspicious, attitude of “anti-dialecticians”⁶³³ toward discussing theological issues with the help of logical reasoning. For example, Lanfranc (1005–1089) criticised Berengar of Tours (999–1088) for questioning the belief of the “reality” of the presence of blood and body of Christ in the Eucharist. Lanfranc accused him of using logical reasoning inappropriately. Furthermore, Peter Damian (1007–1072), after attempting to discuss theological issues such as Divine omnipotence and the compatibility of divine prescience and human free will with the help of “human logic,” considered it unsuitable to discuss “the sacraments of the church” with “the purely verbal art.”⁶³⁴ The attempts to explain and research theological issues deeply with the help of logic can be considered evidence of the presence of philosophy in the Middle Ages. So, the spread and discussion of the texts of Aristotle and Arabic commentaries were not a beginning but a continuation of Medieval philosophical and theological debates. Newly translated literature opened new ideas and fields of discourse, but it did not provoke philosophical and theological debates *ex nihilo*.

⁶³² John Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy (480-1150)* (Oxfordshire: Taylor & Francis, 2002), 95.

⁶³³ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 90.

⁶³⁴ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 93.

“The permanent problem” of reconciling Christianity with ancient philosophy took various approaches during the eleventh century. Scholars such as Peter Damian, Otloh of St. Emmeram (1010–1072), and Gerard of Czanad (980–1046), for example, believed it was not worthwhile to spend time on secular literature.⁶³⁵ However, discussions and attempts to find reason and explanations within theological doctrines remained very important. Anselm (1033–1109), for instance, asserted that “by the use of reason, the Christian can give an understanding of what he already believes.”⁶³⁶ He believed that theologians should attempt to think and find reasons for how divine mysteries can be explained. The accelerated interest in logic during the eleventh and twelfth centuries led to the discovery of Boethius' translations: the *Prior Analytics*, *Topics*, and *Sophistici elenchi*.⁶³⁷ Moreover, Throughout the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, newly translated philosophical and scientific works of Aristotle, such as the texts on natural philosophy and metaphysics, as well as Arabic commentaries by Al-Kindi (801–873), Al-Farabi (870–950), Avicenna (980–1037), and Averroes (1126–1198), became available to the Christian West in Latin. Italian cleric James of Venice (...-1147) completed the translation of the logical corpus with the *Posterior Analytics* from Greek. Subsequently, he translated the *Physics*, *De anima*, *Metaphysics*, five of the *Parva Naturalia* treatises, and an anonymous introduction.⁶³⁸ Some books were translated from Greek, and others from Arabic. For example, Books I-III of *Meteorologica* were translated from Arabic by Gerard of Cremona (1114–1187), and Book IV from Greek by Henricus Aristippus (1105–1162). Gerard of Cremona also translated *Physics*, *De caelo*, *De generatione et corruptione*, *Posterior Analytics*, and Themistius' paraphrase of *Posterior Analytics*, all from Arabic.⁶³⁹

The majority of Aristotle's works were translated in the twelfth century, however, evidence from manuscripts and other sources, such as references to Aristotle's texts, indicates that they were not widely circulated until the thirteenth century.⁶⁴⁰ It is also probable that the establishment of the first European universities facilitated the spreading of the newly translated texts among students and scholars. Given that a significant portion of the thirteenth-century debates occurred within the university environment, that was

⁶³⁵ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 87

⁶³⁶ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 95.

⁶³⁷ Bernard G. Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” in *The Cambridge History of Later Medieval Philosophy from the Rediscovery of Aristotle to the Disintegration of Scholasticism 1100-1600*, eds. Norman Kretzmann, Anthony Kenny and Jan Pinborg (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 46.

⁶³⁸ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 46.

⁶³⁹ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 47.

⁶⁴⁰ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 46.

reflected in the thirteenth-century academic condemnations at the University of Paris (the cases of 1241, 1270, and 1277).⁶⁴¹

Aristotelian ideas about the eternity of the world, the unicity of human intellect, free will, ordained power of God, etc., contradicted Christian doctrines and were considered heretical by the Church. As a result, ecclesiastical authorities started to act against the great quantity of non-Christian literature and began dealing with them by pronouncing condemnations.

Thirteen-Century Condemnations

One of the clear manifestations that Aristotle's books were already widely spread at the beginning of the thirteenth century is the condemnation of 1210.⁶⁴² Petrus de Corbolio (died in 1222), the archbishop of Sens, convened a local council in Sens with the participation of the bishop of Paris, Peter of Nemours, and other bishops to burn the *Quaternuli* of David of Dinant (1160–1217), one of the Amalricians,⁶⁴³ and forbid reading the books of Aristotle and their commentaries publicly or privately. Furthermore, they made a warning that the *Credo in Deum* and *Pater Noster* and several theological books translated into French,⁶⁴⁴ aside from the life of saints, which had already undergone purification, should have been delivered to the bishop of Paris. Anyone found with these religious texts, *Quaternuli*, or Aristotle's works would be considered a heretic.⁶⁴⁵ In 1210, fourteen individuals were condemned. Ten of them were degraded and sent to secular court, where they were burnt at the stake, while the remaining four were imprisoned perpetually.⁶⁴⁶ Here, one can see the influence of the recently introduced inquisitorial procedure for the prosecution of heretics.⁶⁴⁷ Usually, clerics,

⁶⁴¹ The condemnation of 1241 in Heinrich Denifle and Aemilio Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, vol. 1 (Paris: ex Typis Fratrum Delalain, 1889), 170, no. 128. Further references to the first volume of *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis* will be abbreviated CUP; The condemnation of 1270 in CUP, 486, no. 432; The condemnation of 1277 in CUP, 543, no. 473.

⁶⁴² CUP, 70, no. 11.

⁶⁴³ A sect emerged in the twelfth century, associated with the teachings of Amalric of Bena (1150-1207), a master in the faculty of theology in Paris. He himself was condemned in 1206, shortly before his death. As Hans Thijssen writes in his book *Censure and Heresy at the University of Paris 1200-1400* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1998), "In brief, the heresies attributed to the Amalricians can be grouped around three themes: pantheism, the attainment of spiritual perfection here on earth, and the antinomian and antisacramental implications of the Amalricians' views on the preceding two topics."

⁶⁴⁴ Lynn Thorndike, *University Records and Life in the Middle Ages* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1944), 26-27, no. 14.

⁶⁴⁵ CUP, 70, no. 11.

⁶⁴⁶ Hans Thijssen, "Master Amalric and the Amalricians: Inquisitorial Procedure and the Suppression of Heresy at the University of Paris," *Speculum* 71, no. 1 (Januray 1996), 61.

⁶⁴⁷ Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 61.

and therefore, the members of the University, enjoyed the *Privilegium Fori*. According to the privilege, they were exempt from secular courts, even in criminal cases. However, this was changed after issuing the decretal *Vergentis in Senium* by Innocent III (1161–1216) and the reform of 1205–1206 by King Philip Augustus (1165–1223), that the degraded cleric would be handed not directly to a secular court but would be taken to an external place to punish him without committing sacrilege.⁶⁴⁸ A similar thing happened in 1210. Clerics were degraded at the Saint-Honore church and were taken to Champeaux, outside the walls of Paris to burn them at the stake.⁶⁴⁹

Subsequently, the papal legate Robert of Courçon renewed the condemnation in 1215.⁶⁵⁰ More exactly, he was charged with reorganising studies and improving the condition of scholars in Paris to keep the peace among them (*scolarum tranquillitati*). He re-established the condemnation of the teachings of David of Dinant and Amalric of Bene. Besides, he permitted reading all of logic and ethics but forbade lecturing on the texts of Aristotle on metaphysics and natural philosophy as well as commentaries or summaries of them.⁶⁵¹ Apparently, the papal legate banned these texts since they were the main sources of philosophical and scientific thinking and discussions at the university. Reading these texts raised questions among students and scholars that were considered hazardous for Christian doctrines.

In 1225 Pope Honorius III established the condemnation of the *Periphyseon* by John Scottus Eriugena (815–877), referring to it as having been “justly condemned”⁶⁵² by the archbishop of Sens. This means that most probably it was also condemned in 1210. The important point is that the work of Eriugena was connected to Amalric’s heresy, condemned in 1210 as well as at the fourth Lateran Council. Archbishop of Odo of Tuscany, who also participated in the condemnation of 1210 in Paris mentioned that “the impious dogma of Amalric is collected in the book of Master John the Scot.”⁶⁵³ Therefore, one can conclude that

⁶⁴⁸ John W. Baldwin, “Le Contexte Politique et Institutionnel,” in *Les Débuts de L’enseignement Universitaire à Paris (1200 - 1245 Environ)*, eds., Jacques Verger and Olga Weijers (Tournhout : Brepols Publishers, 2013), 23.

⁶⁴⁹ Baldwin, “Le Contexte Politique,” 23.

⁶⁵⁰ CUP, 78, no. 20.

⁶⁵¹ CUP, 78, no. 20.

⁶⁵² CUP, 106, no. 50.

⁶⁵³ This citation of Odo is made by Henry Suso and it is quoted by Stephen Lahey, “Eriugena’s Condemnation and His Idealism,” in *A Companion to John Scottus Eriugena*, ed., Adrian Guiu (Leiden: Brill, 2020), 449.

the condemnation of 1225 was connected to the earlier condemnations of Amalric since the source of his heretical teachings has been associated with the *Periphyseon*.

Furthermore, Pope Gregory IX issued warning letters in 1228 and 1231. In 1228, he advised regent masters in theology not to adulterate God's word by the figments of Philosophers,⁶⁵⁴ and in 1231, he stated that Master of Arts faculty should not use *libros illos naturales*, which had been forbidden in *Concilium provinciali* until they were examined and purged of all suspicion errors. Besides that, he advised Masters and scholars of theology not to declare themselves philosophers but to strive to be *theodocti*.⁶⁵⁵

As Charles H. Lohr writes, the changes in the learning of the faculty of arts are noticeable in a thirteenth-century manuscript in Barcelona in the Archives of the Crown of Aragon, which contains a manual or guidebook for the benefit of students who had to prepare for examinations in the Arts Faculty in Paris.⁶⁵⁶ This text, composed about 1230–40 by an unknown master of the faculty contains the newly translated works and so, reveals the direction which the development of the faculty took in the period. He establishes the works of Aristotle on metaphysics and natural philosophy condemned in 1210 and 1215 as part of *trivium* and *quadrivium*. Therefore, as one can notice, the condemnation did not have an influence in 1230–1240 anymore. As the author conveys, the arts faculty changed its guidance from teaching simply the seven liberal arts of the *trivium* and *quadrivium* to rather all the philosophical and scientific disciplines newly recovered at his time.⁶⁵⁷

Subsequently, there was the condemnation of 1241, which is the first condemnation listing not certain individuals or texts but only erroneous ideas.⁶⁵⁸ The list contains ten banned propositions. The document says that the condemnation was established by the bishop of Paris, William of Auvergne (1190–1249), the chancellor, Odo of Chateauroux (1190–1273), and all masters of the faculty of theology. The involvement of the chancellor and masters of the faculty of theology in the process demonstrates the increase of their role and importance in doctrinal issues of the university if one compares it to the previous cases when only the Pope or bishops participated in the decision.⁶⁵⁹ As Courtenay writes, depending on the

⁶⁵⁴ CUP, 114, no. 59.

⁶⁵⁵ CUP, 136, no. 79.

⁶⁵⁶ Charles H. Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," in *Later Medieval Philosophy*, eds. Kretzmann, Kenny and Pinborg, 84.

⁶⁵⁷ MS Ripoll 109 f. 134^r – 158^v, as quoted in Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 86.

⁶⁵⁸ CUP, 170, no. 128.

⁶⁵⁹ Deborah Grice, *Church, Society and University* (New York: Taylor & Francis group, 2020), 22–31.

information contained in the numerous versions of the opening line of the condemnation decree, it started on the episcopal level since the initiator of the condemnation was the bishop of Paris, William of Auvergne.⁶⁶⁰ Besides that, it is important to underline that the condemnation of 1241 can be considered the first academic condemnation at the University of Paris. As Hans Thijssen singled out there were two important features of academic condemnations: 1. "Cases of academic censure were initiated in the institutional context of the university,"⁶⁶¹ and 2. "The judicial proceedings against an allegedly erring academic focused on suspect statements and views, and not on the holder of those views."⁶⁶² Guided by this definition, the case of 1241 satisfies both aspects.

Despite these prohibitions and warnings, it is known that already in 1245, Roger Bacon made comments on Aristotle's *libri naturales* and metaphysics in Paris.⁶⁶³ In 1255 the statutes of the Arts Faculty were renewed and incorporated practically the whole corpus of Aristotle: Ethics, Physics, Metaphysics, *De animalibus*, *De caelo*, *Meteorologica* (Books I and IV), etc.⁶⁶⁴ Thus, after that, the Faculty of Arts developed a teaching philosophy independent of the Faculty of Theology.⁶⁶⁵ Such a development aroused violent reactions and rivalry between the two faculties.⁶⁶⁶ The incompatibility of theological and philosophical-scientific ideas and the conflicts between scholars at the faculty of arts and theology among a number of topics were revealed in the condemnation of 1270 and 1277 by the Bishop of Paris, Etienne Tempier (...-1279).⁶⁶⁷ He condemned thirteen theses, deemed heretical, in the first case and two hundred and nineteen in the second. It can be said that this so-called technique of publishing condemnations became the tool to defend Christianity from heretical teachings and prevent "corrupting the minds" of scholars and students from philosophical and scientific ideas. Apparently, the goal of these condemnations was not only to prohibit talking and lecturing about the ideas but also *tranquillitas scholarum*, as it was indicated in the condemnation of 1210, to cease debates and controversies between scholars and disclose the border between Christian doctrine and heretical views.

⁶⁶⁰ William J. Courtenay, "Dominicans and Suspect Opinion in the Thirteenth Century: The Cases of Stephen of Venizy, Peter of Tarentaise, and the Articles of 1270 and 1271," *Vivarium* 32, no. 2 (1994): 189.

⁶⁶¹ Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 49.

⁶⁶² Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 49.

⁶⁶³ Fernand Van Steenberghen, *La philosophie au XIIIe siecle* (Paris: Béatrice-Nauwelaerts, 1966), 143.

⁶⁶⁴ CUP, 277, no. 246.

⁶⁶⁵ Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 87.

⁶⁶⁶ Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 87.

⁶⁶⁷ The Condemnation of 1270 in CUP, 486; The Condemnation of 1277 in CUP, 543, no. 473.

The Condemnation of 1277

While the previous condemnations were instigated by ecclesiastical authorities, the initiators of the cases of 1270 and 1277 are still ambiguous. It is known that sixteen theology masters assisted Tempier in constructing the list of propositions in the case of 1277, but the initiator of the action is still controversial, which will be discussed later in the paper. Similar to the condemnation of 1241, Tempier condemned not certain scholars or theologians but ideas themselves.

The new and distinctive features of Tempier's condemnation raise questions about the jurisdiction and how the procedures and rights of ecclesiastical authorities over the university were stipulated in canon law. The significance of the condemnation seems so influential that Pierre Duhem regarded it as “the birth of modern science.”⁶⁶⁸ While this might be an exaggeration, the influence of the condemnation of 1277 on Scholasticism and medieval thought is evident. The banned propositions reflected the thoughts from the critical works of Thomas Aquinas (1225–1274), Siger of Brabant (1240–1280), and Boethius of Dacia (1240–1284) concerning Aristotelian ideas about free will, the unicity of the human intellect, divine knowledge, the nature of eternity, individuation, virtue, wisdom, as well as every-day-life issues, such as carnal acts, confession, Christian morality, etc.⁶⁶⁹ Besides these two hundred and nineteen theses, Tempier condemned some books, precisely, *De Amore* of Andreas Capellanus (1150–1220), the book of Geomancy, and texts, scrolls, and quatrains on necromancy, sorcery, or invocation of demons. However, they are mentioned only in the introductory letter of Etienne Tempier, prefacing the list of propositions, not explicitly among these two hundred and nineteen propositions.⁶⁷⁰ However, a textual analysis of the document suggests that an organisational structure can be found there. While reading the list of propositions, it is evident that there is a certain logic beyond the propositions, especially when one pays attention to the vocabulary used. Ostensibly, there are certain groups concerning one problematic topic or idea. Nevertheless, frequently unrelated articles are interjected. It

⁶⁶⁸ Pierre Duhem, *Etudes sur Leonard de Vinci*, vol. 1 (Paris : Hermann, 1906-1913), 412.

⁶⁶⁹ About free will in Article 102, CUP, 543, no. 473; the unicity of the human intellect in Article 117, CUP, 543, no. 473; divine knowledge in Article 13, CUP, 543, no. 473; the nature of eternity in Article 86, CUP, 543, no. 473; individuation in Article 116, CUP, 543, no. 473; virtue in Article 116, CUP, 543, no. 473; wisdom in Article 154, CUP, 543, no. 473; carnal acts in Article 172, CUP, 543, no. 473; confession in Article 179, CUP, 543, no. 473; Christian morality in Article 183, CUP, 543, no. 473.

⁶⁷⁰ Steenberghen, *La philosophie*, 483. Pierre Mandonnet, *Siger De Brabant et L'Averroisme Latin au XIIIe Siècle* (Fribourg, 1899), 229.

is possible that the articles had a series of headings during a preparatory phase of the censorship, as is presented in *Collectio Errorum in Anglia et Parisius Condemnatorum*.⁶⁷¹ Some proposals could have been misplaced or moved later, accidentally or deliberately, when preparing the final version of the decree. However, there is not yet a specific answer in today's scholarship.⁶⁷²

While the philosophical side of the condemnation of 1277 has been researched by various scholars, political and procedural aspects are frequently left aside. However, there still are several authors who were concerned with that side of condemnation: Gregory Moule, Hans Thijssen, William Courtenay, Andrew Larsen, and Sylvain Piron.⁶⁷³

Concerning the question of who had the authority to establish academic condemnations at the university, Courtenay wrote that in the thirteenth century, the corporation of regent masters took over the task of policing academic orthodoxy, but it is not stated who or what granted this power to them, whether they regularly existed in the thirteenth century or it was formed by ecclesiastical authorities only in certain cases.⁶⁷⁴ For example, as John of Pouilly writes, a commission of sixteen theology masters assisted bishop Etienne Tempier in composing condemned propositions in 1277, but it is not discussed what necessitated this action of the bishop - canon law, common practice, or simply his will to discuss the ideas with scholars.⁶⁷⁵ Clarifying these issues will explain not only Tempier's action of forming the commission but also the function of the corporation of theology masters. Gregory Moule is the only one who examined academic heresy and corporate jurisdiction, concentrating on the rules and procedures set down in canon law. However, his discussion is more general and does not reflect concrete cases of academic heresy in the thirteenth century.⁶⁷⁶

⁶⁷¹ C. du Plessis d'Argentré, ed., *Collectio errorum in anglia et parisius condemnatorum*, in *Collectio juridiciorum de novis erroribus*, vol. 1 (Paris, 1728), 188–200.

⁶⁷² On this issue, please refer to Sylvain Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque pour une critique interne de la condamnation du 7 Mars 1277," *Recherches de théologie et philosophie médiévales* 78, no. 2 (2011): 383–415. He argues quite convincingly about the architecture and arrangement of Tempier's condemnations and makes several substantiated assumptions.

⁶⁷³ Gregory Moule, *Corporate Jurisdiction, Academic Heresy, and Fraternal Correction at the University of Paris, 1200-1400*, vol. 51 of *Education and Society in the Middle Ages and Renaissance* (Leiden: Brill, 2016); Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*; Courtenay, "Inquiry and Inquisition: Academic Freedom in Medieval Universities," *Church History* 58, no. 2 (June 1989); Andrew Larsen, *The School of Heretics, Academic Condemnation at the University of Oxford, 1277-1409* (Leiden: Brill, 2011); Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque."

⁶⁷⁴ Courtenay, "Inquiry and Inquisition," 173.

⁶⁷⁵ John of Pouilly, *Quodlibet* II, 11, quoted in Robert Wielockx, ed., *Aegidii Romani Opera Omnia* III.1 (Florence, 1985), 98.

⁶⁷⁶ Moule, "Corporate Jurisdiction." He discusses several cases of condemnations but from the from the fourteenth century.

The historical background of the condemnations also includes several circumstances that are worth mentioning. On January 18, 1277, Pope John XXI (1215–1277) sent a letter to Etienne Tempier. The Pope stated that he had heard rumours of heresy and charged him with examining where and by whom these errors had been proclaimed at the University of Paris (*facias inspici vel inquiri, a quibus personis et in quibus locis errores hujusmodi dicti sunt sive scripti*).⁶⁷⁷ John XXI did not oblige or authorise him to publish condemnations. He only asked the bishop to investigate and inform back about the outcomes. Tempier instead formed a Commission of sixteen theology masters and published the list of two hundred and nineteen propositions on 7 March 1277, without replying to the Pope.

There is no evidence that the Pope knew of Tempier's condemnation beforehand. Presumably, the bishop made the decision on his own. The arbitrariness of the decision is also supported by the papal letter *Flumen aquae vivae* of April 28.⁶⁷⁸ Here, he already stated the sources of the heretical ideas: “some scholars in the faculties of arts and theology at Paris” (*nonnulli tam in artibus quam in theologica facultate studentes Parisius*)⁶⁷⁹ and mandated Tempier once again to notify him about the results of the investigation. Nevertheless, the action of the bishop remained without any reproach from the papal authorities. It is also important to underline that while the Pope mentioned both scholars in the faculties of arts and theology, Tempier, in his introductory letter prefacing the list of propositions, only referred to scholars in the arts faculty.

Furthermore, there are several theories about what may have provoked Tempier's action to publish condemnation. One of them is that his action was encouraged by Pope John XXI, who, as mentioned above, sent two letters to Tempier.⁶⁸⁰ Another theory proposed by Hans Thijssen is that the bishop was triggered by an inquisitorial investigation by inquisitor Simon du Val. He cited Siger of Brabant, Bernier of Nivelles, and Goswin of Chapelle to appear before his court on November 23, 1276.⁶⁸¹ As Thijssen confers, after that, Tempier could not condemn Siger's ideas *nominatim* according to the juridical principle: *ne bis in idem crimen judicetur*.⁶⁸² Therefore, for Thijssen, this fact seems to be the reason for the anonymity of the

⁶⁷⁷ CUP, 541, no. 471.

⁶⁷⁸ *Archivum Franciscanum Historicum*, vol. 18 (Florence: Quaracchi presso Firenze, 1925), 459–460.

⁶⁷⁹ *Archivum Franciscanum Historicum*, 459.

⁶⁸⁰ Steenberghen, *La Philosophie*, 34.

⁶⁸¹ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 46.

⁶⁸² Gratian's *Decretum*, C.2 q.1 C.14 par.1, cited in Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 48.

condemnations of 1277.⁶⁸³ The argument seems quite convincing, but the fact that the case of 1270 was also anonymous casts serious doubts on the assumption.

Besides that, Sylvain Piron, depending on Tempier's previous arbitrary actions at the university,⁶⁸⁴ claims that he himself promulgated the censorship of the two hundred and nineteen theses.⁶⁸⁵ It is a more common opinion that the condemnations started at the episcopal level.⁶⁸⁶ However, according to his introductory letter: "Repeated accounts of great and serious persons have intimated that a number of students in the arts at Paris are overstepping the boundaries of their own faculty."⁶⁸⁷ So, it is also possible that the bishop was prompted by the "reports" of university scholars.

⁶⁸³ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 38–48.

⁶⁸⁴ He had an argument with university scholars concerning the teaching license. See Moule, "Corporate Jurisdiction," 53–56.

⁶⁸⁵ Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque."

⁶⁸⁶ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy at the University of Paris 1200-1400* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1998), 43.

⁶⁸⁷ CUP, 543, no. 473.

Conclusion

One can safely conclude that the publishing of academic condemnations began in the middle of the thirteenth century, taking the case of 1241 as a starting point. It was the first instance where university members, specifically the chancellor and the masters of the faculty of theology, were involved. Previous condemnations, except the case of 1215, were not explicitly connected to the university. However, since in 1210, Master William of Poitiers is said to have been condemned,⁶⁸⁸ and in 1225, schoolmen are mentioned as readers of *Periphyseon*, one can say that they still touched the university environment.⁶⁸⁹ In the end, the distinctive features of the condemnation of 1277 have to be emphasised. Firstly, it is the largest condemnation of the thirteenth century, with two hundred and nineteen banned propositions established. Other distinguishing characteristics include the summoning of a commission of sixteen Theology Masters, the role of the Pope's letter, reference to only the Faculty of Arts, anonymity and the ambiguity concerning the initiator of the action. These features need further research to reveal important methodological aspects and the extent of involvement of ecclesiastical authorities in university issues. Elaborating on Canon Law is crucial for distinguishing the procedures of condemning heresy and identifying the authorities who were obliged, whether doctrinally or institutionally, to take action against erroneous ideas.

⁶⁸⁸ Denifle and Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, 70:11.

⁶⁸⁹ Denifle and Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, 106:50, *Quia igitur idem liber, sicut accepimus, in nonnullis monasteriis et aliis locis habetur, et nonnulli claustrales et viri scolastici novitatum forte plus quam expediat amatores, se studiosius occupant dicti libri.*

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